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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Sequestration of CO₂ from atmosphere in the form of solid carbonates through mineral carbonation is an option for reduction of CO₂ concentration. In the present study carbon dioxide sequestration has been performed by using sulfatized hydrated mixture of fly ash with calcium bearing material in presence of some chemical activator. Hydrated mixture of both these materials provides a favorable condition for mineral carbonation. TGA study indicates that by suitable conditioning 1ton of carbonated ash absorbs 100kg of CO₂ in atmospheric condition.

Keywords –Mineral carbonation, industrial waste, fly ash, hydrated mixture, and CO₂ sequestration.

INTRODUCTION

Global warming of Earth is a direct consequence of anthropogenic emission of greenhouse gases like CO₂ (IPCC, 2007). In recent years the amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere has gone up to 391.19 ppm in 2011 (ESRL, 2011). More than 7Gtons of anthropogenic CO₂ are released to the atmosphere only from the production of steel each year (Liu and Zhao, 2000). The CO₂ causes about 6-29% of the green house effect on the earth (Kiehl, 1997) and participates in global warming and climate change. Among the prospective technologies for CO₂ fixation, this paper will focus on mineral carbonation, which can be a suitable option for both CO₂ fixation and pollutant stabilization. Carbonation can occur naturally by the reaction between alkaline materials and atmospheric CO₂, but the natural reaction is very slow (Huijgen and Comans, 2003; Sipilä et al., 2008). Mineral carbonation is a naturally occurring weathering process for trapping of CO₂ from the atmosphere where alkaline earth metals (Ca, Mg, Fe) combine with CO₂ to form stable carbonates. The process of mineral carbonation via CO₂ bonding in the natural mineral resources is a phenomenon of aging of rocks in the atmospheric conditions (Kojima et al., 1997).

One major benefit of CO₂ sequestration via mineral carbonation consists of the environmentally benign and virtually permanent trapping of CO₂ in the form of carbonated minerals by using abundant mineral resources (Metz et al., 2005). In terrestrial ecosystem the CO₂ pressure can decrease in the long term as a consequence of mineral carbon sequestration. The stored CO₂ may transform to stable carbonate minerals by reaction with aqueous ions (mainly Ca, Mg & Fe) resulting from weathering of silicates (Gunter et al., 2000; Kaszuba et al., 2003; Kaszuba et al., 2005; Giammar et al., 2005). The basic concept of CO₂ sequestration through mineral carbonation is to mimic natural weathering process in which calcium and magnesium silicates are transformed into carbonates.

Mineral sequestration of CO₂ in controlled reactors have been approached as a viable source to reduce CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere using liquid or solid alkaline residues such as municipal-waste combustion fly-ash, coal combustion fly-ash and alkaline wastes etc (Soong et al., 2006; Huijgen et al., 2006; Huijgen et al., 2007). Mineral carbonation has the advantage that the CO₂ is permanently locked away and no further treatment is required. So it can never be released to the atmosphere if it is not exposed to acidic pH. Ecologically mineral carbonation is a safe way for CO₂ sequestration.

During the present study emphasis has been given on use of industrial solid wastes as possible feed stock for CO₂ sequestration through mineral carbonation. Carbonation of alkaline solid residue can lead to an improvement of their environmental quality (Fallman, 2000; Kostka and Luther III, 1994). The major generators of industrial solid wastes are the thermal power plant. In India presently about 110 million tonnes of coal ash is generated from more

than 70 thermal power plants (Sarkar et al., 2005). It is predicted that, 170 million tones of fly ash will be generated per annum by the year 2012 (Rujamane, 2003). The requirement of land by 2012 for disposal of fly ash slurry will go up to 1000000 acres (Verma et al., 2007). The thermal power plant industries produce million tons of coal fly ash each year, which the industries dispose off several million tons annually in piles, quarries and landfills. Presence of toxic elements like Al, NH₃, As, Ba, Cd, Cl, Cr, Pb, Hg, Ni, Se, SiO₂, SO₄ and Zn in the effluents of ash ponds of the coal fired power plant and the presence of heavy metals in the fly ash leachates causes ground water pollution problem (Phung et al., 1978; ASCE, 1979; Ka KaaKinen et al., 1975). Therefore waste neutralization through carbon sequestration may be an encouraging means to both capture carbon and mitigate the possible adverse health and environmental effects posed by improper disposal of fly ash. The carbonation of alkaline material is an inexpensive and safe process which leads to the formation of thermodynamically stable products (Huijen et al., 2005). There are no commercially available, industry-wide technologies for removing and storing atmospheric CO₂. This paper represents a simplified method to observe the suitability of fly ash to sequester atmospheric CO₂ through mineral carbonation process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fly ash an industrial solid waste is the combustion residue of coal-burning electric power plant composed of spherical micro particles. Viewed from significant differences in its mineralogical composition and properties, it is a pozzolano material that consists of silicate glass and is modified by aluminum and iron as the experimental raw material. The fly ash used in the present study is a solid waste residue generated from thermal power plant and composed of spherical micro particles. Mineral carbonation experiment has been carried in the open place exposed to the atmosphere. In order to observe the curiosity of carbonation and to quantify the amount of CO₂ absorption in fly ash, the mixtures are prepared on 200-300 kg scale. Considering the reaction path of alumina and iron bearing minerals for carbonation, calcium bearing sulfatized mixtures of fly ash has been prepared with suitable additives in presence of water. The pH of the sulfatized mixture of fly ash varies within 9.8-11.0. The sulfatized mixture of fly ash is disposed in to open place exposed to atmospheric condition for 30 days. The mixtures are kept in wet condition by addition of water for weathering and chemical reaction of mineral constituents.

Materials characterization

The chemical composition of fly ash used for carbonation study has been determined by X-ray fluorescence. The mineralogical characterization of the carbonated material of fly ash has been carried out by X-ray diffraction method to examine the presence of different mineral phases. The degree of carbonation of the carbonated material has been examined by Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA). The CO₂ absorption has been estimated from the decomposition of carbonate phases at temperature between 500-900°C.

RESULTS

The chemical composition of fly ash used in experimental study is given in Table-1. The material contain very trace amount of oxides of Na, Mg, Ca, S, Mn, Cr, Ti and rich in alumina and silica. XRD pattern reveals that the fly ash contains mostly oxide and silicate minerals such as quartz, mullite, and hematite (Figure-1a) and the carbonated ash shows presence of some new mineral phases such as calcite (CaCO₃), meionite [Ca₄Al₆(SiO₄)₆.(SO₄.CO₃)] and scawtite (CaO₇.(CO₃) Si₆O₁₈. 2H₂O) (Figure-1b). Thermo gravimetric analysis indicates that the fly ash exposed for carbonation reaction shows weight loss at 150°C - 200°C and 700°C - 800°C (Figure-2(a) and 2(b), which has been discussed in the text.

Table 1: Chemical analysis of fly ash

Constituent %	Na ₂ O	MgO	PO ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	CaO	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Cr ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃
Fly ash	0.09	0.285	0.51	0.14	0.47	35.5	59.5	0.94	0.01	2.01

Figure 2 (b): Thermo Gravimetric Analysis of carbonated fly ash

DISCUSSION

Fly ash is sulfatised in presence of calcium bearing material to initiate the chemical reaction in atmospheric condition. The chemical reaction proceeds through decomposition and dissolution of silicates in alkaline condition to form intermediate sulfate bearing minerals. These minerals are unstable and react with CO_2 to form carbonates. The possible reaction path of sulfatised fly ash mixture during the carbonation is as follows

The carbonation reaction is a complex process and many intermediate mineral structures are observed. The mineral phases of carbonated ash observed through XRD pattern (Figure-1b) resembles to calcite (CaCO_3), meionite [$\text{Ca}_4\text{Al}_6(\text{SiO}_4)_6 \cdot (\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{CO}_3)$] and scawtite ($\text{CaO}_7 \cdot (\text{CO}_3) \text{Si}_6\text{O}_{18} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) which are formed during carbonation process of fly ash. These carbonated minerals decompose between 700°C - 800°C temperatures due to the loss of CO_2 from the structure (Figure-2a). Calcium rarely occurs as binary oxides in nature. During the experimental process the reaction initiates by the thorough mixing of fly ash with gypsum in presence of water. Dissolution of silica and alumina of fly ash in presence of calcium and sulfate form the mineral structure ettringite ($3\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 32\text{H}_2\text{O}$), which is an intermediate product and also unstable. Ettringite is further decomposed to form carbonate and sulphate mineral phases. Therefore ettringite is usually absent in carbonated ash. These minerals are capable of being carbonated because carbonic acid is a stronger acid than silicic acid. Thus silica present in the mineral is exchanged with carbonate and the mineral is being carbonated. As carbonate is the lowest energy state of carbon, mineral carbonation for CO_2 sequestration is a strongly exothermic reaction process and occurs slowly in atmospheric reaction due to gradual physicochemical weathering of silicates minerals present in fly ash. It is observed that through sulfation reaction in presence of calcium, the mineral constituents of fly ash undergo structural transformation and formation of carbonated mineral. The free CaO and MgO present in fly ash the ability to bind CO_2 (Johnson, 2000; Back et al., 2006a; Baciocchi et al., 2006). The atmospheric carbonation is a slow process. So to find out the CO_2 sequestration potentiality, the samples after 30 days of atmospheric exposure are collected to observe and characterize about the formation of carbonate phases. The quantitative estimation of CO_2 absorption through mineral carbonation is calculated from the thermal analysis by the mass loss. From the experimental study it is found that fly ash is absorbing CO_2 from the atmosphere through mineral carbonation. The de-carbonation temperature is assigned to loss from the thermo gravimetric analysis (Figure 2 (a) and (b)) that the fly ash in the process of sulfation reaction forms carbonated mineral phases.

The decomposition of carbonated products starts from 500°C . Temperatures are only indicative because they depend on the extension of the precedent peak and on the matter quantity. The peak shape also depends on the carbonate stability, and progress of the carbonation process (Villain et al., 2007). From the TGA graph of carbonated fly ash it is found that 1 tonne of fly ash mixture is absorbing 100 kg of CO_2 in atmospheric condition.

Cost economics

Mineral carbonation of fly ash is cost-effective and it requires atmospheric condition like disposal through stock piling in the field. Fly ash along with suitable sulphate bearing material and carbon stimulating chemical is used for carbonation reaction. This reaction process proceeds in humid condition in presence of water and form unstable hydrated minerals of calcium aluminium sulphate compounds which on CO₂ absorption decomposes to carbonated phases. It is estimated that in one ton fly ash treatment the cost of additive will be 20-25 rupees. This cost factor may vary depending upon the local condition, quantity and availability of the raw material.

It is necessary to measure quantitative carbonation profiles to monitor the carbonation progress over time.

CONCLUSIONS

Present study reveals that fly ash has carbonation capacity which proceeds through sulfation reaction under atmospheric condition. Mineral carbonation is a chemical sequestration route in which, the products are thermodynamically stable. Therefore the storage of CO₂ is permanent and inherently safe. In this process hydration mechanisms are involved through intermediate unstable phases. The main hydration product detected in the carbonated mixture is calcium carbonate. Direct use of the industrial wastes like fly ash need no mining and consumption of raw material is avoided. Moreover these residues tend to be more reactive for carbonation than primary minerals due to their chemical instability and thus their use might enable a reduction of the energy consumption and costs of mineral CO₂ sequestration. The incorporation of fly ash with calcium bearing material through mineral carbonation can contribute as a good substrate for agriculture and act as a better option for sustainable management of fly ash. As fly ash is slightly alkaline in nature, its reactivity makes it suitable as a feed stock material to absorb CO₂ at low economic and energetic costs.

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